

ESTIMATES OF ZONAL AND MERIDIONAL TRANSPORT VELOCITIES OF ATMOSPHERIC AEROSOLS OF VOLCANIC ORIGIN

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On January 15, 2022, at 04:14:45 UTC, the largest eruption on Earth in the last 30 years occurred at the Hunga-Tonga-Hunga-Hapai volcano (hereinafter referred to as the Tonga volcano). During this event, a large mass of ash was ejected to stratospheric heights above 30 km. The eruption had planetary consequences, causing various geophysical responses. Our research was aimed at finding changes in the concentration of atmospheric aerosols formed as a result of the eruption, both in low-latitude regions close to the eruption and in high latitudes – in Antarctica and the Arctic. The work estimated the zonal and meridional transport velocities of aerosol particles at stratospheric heights.

The study used data from the global aerosol worldwide network AERONET (Holben et al., 1998). Two monitoring points in Australia, 3 in the tropics, and 4 positions each in the Arctic and Antarctica were selected for analysis. The results of registrations of Australian stations were analyzed during January 2022, and for the remaining stations located in the tropics and polar regions, three-year measurement arrays were used (from 2021 to 2023). The aerosol optical thickness (AOT) in two spectral windows for wavelengths – 440 nm or 443 nm (hereinafter AOT440 or AOT443) was chosen as the information parameter. For quantitative assessments and visualization of the research results, data were averaged for each of the three years of observations at all stations.

As a result of the statistical processing of observation data, an increase in the concentration of atmospheric aerosols was established for both polar and tropical regions caused by a super-powerful volcanic eruption. In particular, in just two days, emissions from the Tonga volcano reached the east coast of Australia, and the value of the AOT440 parameter increased from 0.15 units to 2. For another two days, emissions moved with air masses to the west coast of the continent, where AOT443 increased from 0.15 units to 1. The average zonal transport speed in the tropical region was 18 ± 2 m/s.

Studies of changes in aerosol levels in the air of polar regions were carried out by analyzing data from selected monitoring stations in Antarctica and the Arctic for 2021–2023. It was found that in Antarctica the AOT440 value increased on average by 2–3 times only after about one year, and in the Arctic in 2023, the growth was approximately 1.5 to 2 times. Thus, the approximate equivalent meridional velocity of aerosols from the volcano to the polar regions was about two orders of magnitude smaller than the zonal velocity.

Holben B. N., Eck T. F., Slutsker I., Tanre D., Buis J. P., Setzer. A., Vermote E., Reagan J. A., Kaufman Y. J., Nakajima T., Lavenu F., Jankowiak I., & Smirnov A. (1998). AERONET – A Federated Instrument Network and Data Archive for Aerosol Characterization. *Remote Sens. Environ.*, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-4257\(98\)00031-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-4257(98)00031-5)